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THE GRANTING OF PREGNANCY MAINTENANCE TO THE UNBORN CHILD

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the pregnant woman's right to child support. The topic was analyzed with the real objective of discussing in depth the legal protection of the right to maintenance owed to the unborn child and making an analysis in the light of the criteria for recognizing evidence of paternity. Thus, the central problem of this research arose: To what extent is it possible to grant child support in the event of uncertainty about the paternity of the unborn child? The proposed affirmative is in fact true, since the legal system guarantees the unborn child the right to pregnancy maintenance from conception and the doctrine, in turn, presents that the establishment of maintenance based on strong evidence that leads to certainty of paternity is fully possible, since it is a being that has not yet been born. In addition, there are countless precedents in this same line of reasoning, which guarantee maintenance to the unborn child, by means of criteria that lead to the recognition of paternity, such as evidence by magistrates and courts, witnesses, photos, social networks, joint accounts, among others that are explained throughout this article.

KEYWORDS: Maintenance. Pregnancy. Unborn child. Family. Paternity.

INTRODUCTION

On November 5, 2008, Law 11.804/2008 introduced the right to pregnancy maintenance into the Brazilian legal system, the main feature of which is to ensure the protection of the unborn child and automatically the pregnant woman, in view of the vulnerability that exists during the gestational period.

As this rule is seen as very recent, there has been much discussion about the selection of criteria used by the courts to establish the amount that will actually be awarded to the pregnant woman through the figure of the person seen as the supposed parent.

These amounts have the character of alimony and will be determined based on mere indications of paternity, taking into account the trinomial need x possibility x reasonableness, and also the Principles of the Irrepeatability of Alimony, facts that have in fact generated a great deal of discussion in the legal sphere.

This problem gives rise to the research objective: To what extent is it possible to grant child support in the event of uncertainty about the paternity of the unborn child?

The main objective of the research that follows is to answer the proposed problem by analyzing the doctrinal, legal and jurisprudential arguments to be developed in the sessions of the aforementioned Course Conclusion Work.

The first session looks at the existence of the unborn child, and the discussion about which theory should be adopted to determine the exact moment for the acquisition of its legal personality, highlighting the analysis and characteristics of the Natalist, Conceptionist and Conditional Personality Theories.

The importance of the respective institutes is indisputable, since the unborn child, regardless of any theory to be adopted, since the Federal Constitution is seen as a being who has already been given rights, including the right to life, which is guaranteed through the right to

maintenance. The importance of the existence of such regulations for pregnant women and, automatically, for the unborn child, can thus be seen.

The 2nd session will look at the Maintenance Obligation, the current legislation on Pregnancy Maintenance, as well as the subjects, assumptions and existing characteristics. The Magistrates' view of the granting of pregnancy maintenance to the unborn child will also be analyzed, taking into account the criteria used to set the amount that will actually be paid by the alleged father as maintenance.

The 3rd session deals with the rights and duties of the pregnant woman in relation to pregnancy maintenance, showing her as the direct link to maintaining the life of the unborn child. This is the active legitimacy of the action that is sustained so that there is a Grant of Pregnancy Maintenance to the unborn child, and also show what assumptions enable her to be able or not, to come to receive such funds.

In section 4, the figure of the alleged parent is presented, taking into account their rights and duties with regard to child support, showing how they are approached, when they are at the side of the lawsuit, what principles govern them, and what stance they should take with regard to the lawsuit granting child support.

Last but not least is the 5th session, which deals with how the courts have been ruling on the granting of child support when there are doubts about paternity. This session covers the innovations brought in by Law 11.804/2008 to the Brazilian legal system, the evidence that can and cannot be used to claim child support and the stance of magistrates when faced with the denial of paternity, where the case in question identified the bad faith of the pregnant woman, in order to enrich herself, with the characteristics surrounding the Pregnancy Maintenance Law as a trump card.

Law 11.804/2008 gave rise to a series of questions about the legal personality of the unborn child, about maintenance obligations and about

establishing criteria for recognizing paternity, which in turn became the theoretical framework for this research.

Finally, the citations presented were in fact based on the methodologies used, which are the laws that address the subject discussed, bibliographical and doctrinal research on the Pregnancy Maintenance Law (Law 11.804/2008).

DEVELOPMENT

2.1 THE LEGAL PERSONALITY OF THE UNBORN CHILD

The unborn child is characterized as someone who is yet to be born, thus existing inside the mother's womb, but has not yet reached birth. Article 2 of the Brazilian Civil Code of 2002 states that the civil personality of a human being begins with birth, but current legislation protects the rights of the unborn child from conception onwards .

According to our legal system, there are three important theories on the subject: Natalist, Conceptionist and Conditional.

Turning to the Natalist Theory, it can be seen that the unborn child only acquires civil personality when they are born alive, according to the provisions of Article 2 of the Brazilian Civil Code of 2002 .

Maria Helena Diniz points out that the aforementioned article does not set out the requirements of effectiveness and human form, showing that the legal personality of the unborn child begins with the occurrence of live birth, even if the newborn is declared dead moments after its birth .

In view of the above, it is understood that Natalists defend the existence of the legal personality of the unborn child after it is born alive, even if it dies seconds after its birth, at which point the legal effects for the acquisition of its personality are verified

Moving on to the Conceptionist Theory, we see

that it argues that the rights and obligations involving the unborn child actually begin at conception, so before they are born alive, their interests are already protected.

LOUREIRO's understanding is that the legal personality of the unborn child begins at conception, and not after birth, as stated by the Natalist Theory, since many rights pertaining to being conceived are not in fact conditional on birth, such as the rights to be adopted, recognized, represented and personality .

With this understanding, it can be explained why the unborn child can receive maintenance, be a party to legal actions, be an heir and have their rights protected even before their birth, thus being the subject of very personal rights. The Conditional Personality Theory shows that for the legal personality of the unborn child to exist, it must be born alive.

This theory is seen as a true fusion of the Natalist and Conceptionist theories, with a subdivision of the Conceptionist theory. It has the understanding that in fact recognizes the personality of the unborn child from its conception, and is in fact linked to the condition that it be born alive.

For rights to be acquired in relation to the unborn child, the fetus must be born alive. If this occurs, the acquisition is conferred, otherwise there will be no loss or acquisition of their rights, nor will their personality even be recognized . Thus, some scholars claim that the law in fact guarantees the rights of the unborn child during the months of its mother's pregnancy, thus protecting certain rights of a personal and property nature, while there is a suspensive condition which depends exclusively on its live birth.

2.1.1 Maintenance: the obligation to maintain
Since the world was made, we can say that there is no life without food, housing, access to health, education, security, clothing and leisure. This makes it impossible to violate the provision of food, which is a constitutional right and automatically violates the principle of human

dignity.

The right to maintenance has the purpose of satisfying the needs of those who may not be able to actually provide for them, where the Civil Code in its article 1695 shows that “Maintenance is due when those who want it do not have sufficient assets or can provide for their own maintenance through their work, and those from whom it is claimed can provide it without losing what is necessary for their sustenance”.

In Brazilian law, the term food is used as a resource for nutritional survival, extending to housing, health, education, security, leisure, with the real aim of meeting all the needs inherent to human beings, in other words, that they may need throughout their existence in order to have a minimum of dignity.

The doctrine itself establishes protection for children from the moment they are conceived, since there are rights that are recognized as being protected, based on the Brazilian Civil Code and the Statute of the Child and Adolescent.

Parental responsibility has become unquestionable since the conception of the unborn child, thus leading to maintenance obligations.

Affirming this point of our legal system, the duty of the unborn can in fact begin before their birth, since before they are born there are already expenses that are technically intended exclusively for the protection of the unborn.

It can be concluded that the purpose of the right to maintenance is the preservation of life, so it is a matter of public policy, taking into account the trinomial existing in our legal system comprising necessity x possibility x reasonableness, even if the unborn child only acquires legal personality with its birth, as analysts claim, it becomes fundamental to safeguard its rights from its conception, that is, still inside the mother’s womb in order to ensure that its birth takes place alive, as supported by law 11804/2008 (Pregnancy Maintenance Law).

2.1.2 Pregnancy maintenance

Based on the Brazilian Federal Constitution of 1988 and the Brazilian Civil Code of 2002, the right to maintenance is characterized as a fundamental right, aimed directly at every human being.

With the rise of Law 11.804/08, the figure of the unborn child as a holder of legal personality has come into focus, thus entitling them to benefits while still in their mother’s womb.

Still focusing on the aforementioned law, the aim is to analyze and understand the protection that exists in the legal sphere for the rights of unborn children and the criteria that exist in the aforementioned legal system for fixing them.

Law 11894/08 also affirms the active legitimacy of the pregnant woman, who is the active subject of the lawsuit, linked to the obligation to pay maintenance, and is thus seen as the one who will be responsible for filing the Maintenance Action against the alleged parent, even if there is no concrete relationship with them. Once it is only necessary for there to be evidence to suggest that the alleged father is the father of the child being formed in his womb, the Pregnancy Maintenance Claim is established.

These foods will be hung throughout the gestational period.

The unborn child can actually seek alimony, since it is protected by the Brazilian Civil Code of 2002 and the recent Law 11804/08 on Pregnancy Alimony. In fact, such alimony is income intended for the pregnant woman, which will be transformed into alimony when the offspring is born.

At the beginning of November 2008, a historic moment in which Law 11804/08 was published, in force since then, Pregnancy Maintenance was inserted into our legal system, guaranteeing once and for all the right of the unborn child, even before the day of its birth, showing the maintenance obligation since its conception and not necessarily depending on it being seen as the real holder only if it is born alive.

It is through pregnancy maintenance payments

that pregnant women can receive the assistance they need at this difficult time for many of them. These payments are made by the parent to the unborn child, with the real aim of the child being nourished by those actually responsible for its conception.

Thus, the mother has the right to sue the courts from the first signs of pregnancy.

This is the moment when they must clearly and directly explain their real needs, especially their financial needs, and point out who will be recognized as their parent.

Once the preliminary evidence of paternity has been analyzed, which can include eyewitness testimony, the presentation of photos, videos and messages on social networks, all of which are recognized as means of proving that the parent is in fact the one proven in the case file, it is now clear who the child's father is.

It should be noted that it would in fact be possible to carry out a DNA test to prove paternity by removing the amniotic fluid inside the gestational uterus, but this method is not recommended by medicine as it is invasive and very harmful to the development of what is being formed in the uterine space.

Thus, it is enough for the judge to recognize the existence of evidence of paternity for Pregnancy Maintenance to be granted.

In fact, the mere imputation of paternity is not enough, without the pregnant woman presenting legal facts that show the existence of a link with the person who may later be declared the father.

Maintenance is of a public order nature and has two fundamental prerequisites: Necessity, on the part of the person who needs it, and Economic Possibility, on the part of the person who is responsible for providing it. This binomial is analyzed according to each specific case, in accordance with the Principle of Reasonableness. This is in fact analyzed by the competent magistrate, in line with the aforementioned triad Needs x Possibility x Reasonableness.

Pregnancy maintenance payments are those intended for pregnant women so that they can meet the expenses arising from the gestational period and everything that is entirely linked to that period, from conception to the birth of the unborn child.

It is true that such maintenance will last until the birth of the child and will then be converted into alimony, since the judge's discernment becomes fundamental for the resolution of each specific case, analyzing the evidence that must be clear as to the existence of paternity, not denying the alleged father a full defense, also taking into account the bad faith of the pregnant woman, a situation in which it is not allowed to apply the Principle of Unrepeatability of Maintenance, resulting in losses and damages for the offended party.

Thus, pregnancy maintenance is seen as a right that guarantees the protection of the child that is to come, since it is shown to be an aid that has the sole and true purpose of meeting the needs of the human being still in its early stages.

This income is primarily in the possession of the mother when she is pregnant, so that she who does not have the means to support herself with: the food necessary for the development of the fetus, access to quality health care and expenses for exams in general, does not feel helpless during the gestational period, when she is much more physically and psychologically fragile.

2.2 THE RIGHTS AND DUTIES OF PREGNANT WOMEN WITH REGARD TO CHILD SUPPORT

Law 11804/08 recognizes the granting of pregnancy maintenance by the pregnant woman in the first instance as the direct link to maintaining the life of the unborn child while in her womb.

As such, she is the active party in the lawsuit filed against the man she sees as her genitor, according to her and the evidence presented in court, with the subjective triggering event being the existence

of the gestational period she experienced. Law 11804/08 serves as a real tool for guaranteeing and assisting the fetus, since it states that these benefits will be extremely important for preserving the life and dignity of the unborn child, as can be seen in its article:

Art. 2 “The maintenance referred to in this law shall include the amounts sufficient to cover the additional expenses of the period of pregnancy and those arising from it, from conception to childbirth, including those relating to special food, medical and psychological assistance, complementary examinations, hospitalizations, childbirth, medicines and other preventive and therapeutic prescriptions that are indispensable, in the judgment of the doctor, as well as others that the judge deems pertinent.

Sole Paragraph: The maintenance referred to in this article refers to the part of the expenses that must be borne by the future father, taking into account the contribution that must also be made by the pregnant woman, in proportion to the resources of both.”

Responsibility for the preservation of uterine life is reciprocal, since both parents have a duty to care for and preserve the dignity of the unborn child so that it is alive at the end of the gestational period when it is born.

This reciprocal responsibility involving both parents is linked to the economic possibility of each one, as we can see between the lines of paragraph 1 of article 1.694 of the Brazilian Civil Code of 2002, stating that maintenance should be set in proportion to the needs of the claimant and the resources of the person obliged, evidencing the Principle of Proportionality.

It is clear from the Brazilian legal system that the pregnant woman has the right to be granted pregnancy maintenance, as she is seen as the main and important source for the unborn child to develop inside the uterus and reach birth.

It is also her right to file this action against the alleged parent, with the main aim of safeguarding

the life of their child, who is still being formed. Since the law is entirely clear about ensuring the life of the unborn child through the maternal figure.

It is essential that the facts are true in relation to the assumption of paternity, since art. 6 of the law analyzed makes it clear that the moment the plaintiff (mother) proves the evidence of paternity, the judge is already able to set child support.

Thus, she (the pregnant woman) must act ethically, morally, in good faith and truthfully, and it is certain that if bad faith is shown, she will be penalized, since such conduct means that the Principle of Unrepeatability of Maintenance does not really apply, resulting in losses and damages.

Considering what is expressed in article 186 of the Brazilian Civil Code of 2002, it is clear that anyone who, through voluntary action or omission, negligence or recklessness, violates a right and causes damage to another, even if exclusively moral, commits an unlawful act. In this way, it is clear that if the fault of the pregnant woman (the plaintiff) is proven, that she acted with a deliberate desire to cause harm to her parent (the defendant), or negligence and recklessness, by filing the lawsuit, it shows that this rule, seen as the foundation of civil liability, is in fact above the Principle of Unrepeatability of Alimony, which is characterized by the fact that if the amounts referring to any alimony are paid unduly, it is not possible to demand their return.

It is clear that with the veto of article 10 of Law 11804/08, which stated that if the result of the paternity test is negative, the plaintiff will be objectively liable for the material damage caused to the defendant, and in its sole paragraph emphasized that the compensation would be settled in the case file itself.

This article was vetoed due to the fact that it was an intimidating rule, as it created the hypothesis of strict liability, based on the fact of filing a lawsuit and not succeeding, showing that the exercise of the right to file a lawsuit in itself could already cause damage to third parties, leading the plaintiff to have the duty to indemnify, regardless

of the existence of guilt.

Today, while the plaintiff (pregnant woman) can and should file a lawsuit for child support against the defendant (genitor), the defendant can also have his or her rights protected in terms of proving that the denial of paternity is justified, as soon as the plaintiff's (genitor's) bad faith is proven.

DIAS, states that when the creditor's bad faith or malicious attitude is in fact proven, in the name of Irrepeatability, it cannot lead to unjustified enrichment, being called the relativity of non-restitution.

Since the defendant is no longer seen as a parent, under the Brazilian legal system, in accordance with the rule contained in art. 186 of the Brazilian Civil Code of 2002, the right to compensation for moral and material damages is guaranteed.

2.3 THE RIGHTS AND DUTIES OF THE ALLEGED PARENT WITH REGARD TO CHILD SUPPORT

Preliminarily, it is worth pointing out that Pregnancy Maintenance is understood to be the expenses arising from the gestational period. This period is extremely important for maintaining a woman's life, taking into account her special diet, having access to a quality health network, complementary exams, in order to be physically and psychologically healthy, with the real aim of preserving the life of the person in her womb.

Based on these statements in the Brazilian legal system, it is important to note the existence of Law 11804/08, on Pregnancy Maintenance, which has brought balance and fairness to the criteria for setting amounts, given the expenses involved for the mother and the supposed father of the unborn child.

As such, these expenses stem from the gestational period from the conception of the unborn child to its birth. This is an obligation of a divisible nature, since it is clear that both parents are jointly responsible for the developing being and automatically for all the expenses associated with it in order to preserve its life until the day it is born.

It should be noted that this law differs from alimony in that the amounts relating to the gestational period will be divided between the mother and the alleged father in proportion to their incomes, in accordance with the Principle of Proportionality.

If paternity is proven, such maintenance is automatically reverted to child support; as Law 11804/08 states in its 6th article, let's see:

Convinced of the existence of evidence of paternity, the judge will set a time limit until the birth of the child, taking into account the needs of the plaintiff and the possibilities of the defendant.

Sole Paragraph: After the birth of a child, maintenance payments are converted into alimony in favor of the child until one of the parties requests a review.

VENOSA states that the most significant innovation brought about by this law is that presented in its 6th article.

The defendant in the lawsuit is the alleged father, who is exposed by the pregnant woman, who is the active party in the pregnancy maintenance lawsuit against the unborn child. She is responsible for presenting the evidence to prove paternity, evidence which, in view of what has already been analyzed, does not need to be very robust, so the pregnant woman must bring to the case file elements that can somehow demonstrate that the defendant is the father.

Such evidence can include photos and messages on social networks, e-mails, proof of joint expenses, among others. Facts and evidence that the judge will take into account in Article 6 of Law 11804/08, leading to the granting of the Pregnancy Maintenance Action.

Since the DNA paternity test is seen by medical experts as invasive and harmful to those inside the mother's womb, it can be carried out after the birth of the child.

After the birth of the unborn child, after the paternity test has been carried out and it has

been proven that the alleged father is not the father of the child, there may be the possibility of compensation for moral and material damages against the mother.

The legal basis for the lawsuit is Article 186 of the Brazilian Civil Code of 2002, which states that anyone who, through voluntary action or omission, recklessness or negligence, causes damage to others and violates their rights, commits an unlawful act. The same applies to article 187 of the Brazilian Civil Code of 2002, which states that the holder of a right who, in exercising it, manifestly exceeds the limits imposed by its economic or social purpose, good faith or good customs, also commits an unlawful act.

According to article 928 of the Brazilian Civil Code of 2002, those who cause damage to others through an unlawful act (articles 186 and 187) are obliged to make reparation. It is clear that the possible obligation to compensate is based on the unlawful act practiced with intent or fault.

The author Maria Helena Diniz states that in order to characterize a wrongful act, the following must be present:

Therefore, for it to be characterized, there must be a voluntary action or omission that violates a legal rule that protects the interests of others or an individual subjective right and that the offender is aware of the illegality of their act, acting with intent, if they intentionally seek to harm others, or guilt, if they are aware of the damage that comes from their act and assume the risk of causing a harmful event.

It is clear that the mother should be held subjectively responsible for having committed an unlawful act, and that she is liable to compensation for moral and material damages if she is proven to have acted in bad faith by presenting the evidence that would prove the identity of the unborn child's paternity. Such behavior can cause great damage to the alleged father in his family, personal, professional and economic life.

In this way, the Civil Liability rule overrides the

Principle of Unrepeatability of Alimony, which means that if the amounts relating to alimony are paid unduly, there will still be no consent to their return.

Finally, it can be seen that the evidence that leads to the assertion of paternity is fragile, and it is essential that the magistrate be cautious in his judgment, analyzing all the requirements that lead to the veracity or otherwise of the alleged paternity.

It is true, however, that if paternity is not proven, the court may make use of the Theory of Flexibility or Relativization of the Principle of Unrepeatability of Maintenance, in order to avoid real injustices to those named as Defendants.

2.4 HOW THE COURTS HAVE RULED ON THE GRANTING OF CHILD SUPPORT WHEN THERE IS DOUBT ABOUT PATERNITY.

In the light of the analysis of pregnancy maintenance, it is seen as the necessary income acquired by the pregnant woman, such as: special and quality food, medical and psychological assistance, examinations in general, hospitalizations, childbirth and other prescriptions that medicine deems necessary so that from conception to childbirth, the unborn child has the means to arrive alive on the day of its birth.

These earnings, which according to the Brazilian legal system, are divisible and proportional, thus deriving from the financial income of both parents, even when there are doubts about paternity.

It is certain that, during this period, the investigation of evidence with the aim of affirming the veracity involving the alleged parent has already been analyzed and upheld by the Magistrate responsible for the specific case in question.

According to the Conceptionist Theory, which shows us that the unborn child is a being endowed with life and rights that are protected

from the moment of conception, we end up with a guarantee of the right to justice, in article 5, item XXXV of the Brazilian Federal Constitution, which translates as “the law shall not exclude from the appreciation of the Judiciary any injury or threat to the right” , even if the form of its exercise is by presentation. It can be concluded that from the moment of conception, the unborn child is already seen as a subject of rights, and is protected by this article.

It should also be noted that the protection of the unborn child can be found in a certain way in Article 6 of the Magna Carta, based on the protection of maternity, in order to understand that if the pregnant woman is safe, involved in all the benefits that help to maintain the offspring, from conception to birth, the same will also be ensured:

Social rights are education, health, food, work, housing, transportation, leisure, security, social security, maternity and childhood protection, and assistance to the destitute, in the form of this Constitution.

Law 11804/08 brought innovations to the legal system when it came to enforcing the Pregnancy Maintenance Lawsuit: the declaration of a kinship relationship is unnecessary to file this lawsuit, and it is enough for the mother to present evidence to the court that leads to an affirmation of the alleged paternity, being the active party in the lawsuit; it is not necessary for the defendant to be summoned in order to force payment of the maintenance claim, in view of the prohibition in Art. 9 of this law. It is also stated that after the birth of the child, the maintenance granted by the alleged father will be reverted to alimony, at which point it will go directly to the child itself and no longer to the mother, until one of the parties files for a review.

What can be observed:

SPECIAL APPEAL. CONSTITUTIONAL. CIVIL. CIVIL PROCEDURE. PREGNANCY MAINTENANCE. GUARANTEE TO PREGNANT WOMEN. PROTECTION OF THE UNBORN CHILD. LIVE BIRTH. TERMINATION OF PROCEEDINGS. NOT OCCURRING.

AUTOMATIC CONVERSION OF CHILD SUPPORT INTO ALIMONY IN FAVOR OF THE NEWBORN. CHANGE OF OWNERSHIP. ENFORCEMENT BY THE MINOR, REPRESENTED BY HIS MOTHER, OF THE UNPAID MAINTENANCE AFTER HIS BIRTH. POSSIBILITY. APPEAL DISMISSED.

1. maintenance payments for pregnancy, provided for in Law 11.804/2008, are intended to help pregnant women with the expenses arising from pregnancy, from conception to childbirth. the pregnant woman is therefore the direct beneficiary of maintenance payments for pregnancy and, consequently, the rights of the unborn child are protected. 2. With the live birth of the child, the maintenance granted to the pregnant woman will automatically be converted into maintenance in favor of the newborn, thus changing the ownership of the maintenance, without the need for a judicial pronouncement or an express request from the party, under the terms of the sole paragraph of art. 6 of Law n. 11.804/2008. (3) As a rule, the action for child support is not extinguished or loses its object with the birth of the child, as the said support is converted into alimony until any review action requesting exoneration, reduction or increase in the amount of support or even any result in an action to investigate or deny paternity. (STJ - REsp: 1629423 SP 2016/0185652-7, Rapporteur: Minister MARCO AURÉLIO BELLIZZE, Date of Judgment: 06/06/2017, T3 - THIRD COURT, Date of Publication: DJe 22/06/2017 RSDF vol. 103 p. 152)

On the basis of the above, it is noted in the Judgment, that the Ministers of the Third Panel of the Superior Court of Justice, in accordance with the votes and the tachygraphic notes, agreed unanimously to dismiss the Special Appeal, in accordance with the vote of the Reporting Justice. This is in accordance with Art. 6 of Law 11.804/08, which states in its sole paragraph that “After the birth of a child, child support is converted into alimony in favor of the child until one of the parties requests a review”.

With the analysis of Law 11804/08 and all its objectives, whether or not it can be established,

it is clear that the Courts have been employing the idea that the Pregnancy Maintenance Action should prosper when evidence is in fact presented that leads to the veracity of the suspicion of paternity, taking into account the discernment, truth and good faith of the mother as the plaintiff, otherwise it will not prosper. Let's see:

INTERLOCUTORY APPEAL.
PROVISIONAL MAINTENANCE FOR
PREGNANT WOMEN. Law 11804/2008 regulates the right to maintenance for pregnant women. However, although it is possible to grant interim maintenance, in the case of an action for maintenance of pregnancy, it is imperative that the claim is accompanied by evidence of paternity. In the absence of any proof of paternity, it is unfeasible to set provisional maintenance. (Interlocutory Appeal No. 70067019372, Seventh Civil Chamber, RS Court of Justice, Rapporteur: Jorge Luís DallAgnol, Judged on 16/12/2015).

Here is the content of the ruling:

(...) In this scenario, in which there is no evidence of the defendant's paternity, it is unfeasible to set provisional maintenance for the time being, which is why the appealed decision should be overturned, revoking the maintenance payments established in the original decision. Therefore, since there is no evidence of paternity to support the granting of child support, the appeal should be dismissed. Accordingly, I grant the interlocutory appeal.

It can be seen that the noble judges, in a unanimous decision, ultimately decided to uphold the appeal and it is clear that there was no truth to the evidence presented in court.

In cases where the genitor's bad faith is proven, in accordance with Article 187 of the Civil Code 2002, the plaintiff becomes the defendant and is responsible for compensating moral damages to the person who was deceived into believing that he was the father of the unborn child, offering him means of survival during the gestational period. This is evident from the following amendment to the appeal, showing the possibility of an action for

compensation for moral damages being filed, the false paternity presented by the plaintiff having been verified, the guilt having been observed, causing damage to the plaintiff.

MORAL DAMAGES. ACCUSATION OF FALSE PATERNITY. Defendant who accused the plaintiff of paternity, while having a relationship with another man during the same period. Plaintiff who later found out that he was not the father of the child through a DNA test. Fault on the part of the defendant. Failure to comply with the duty of care, resulting from the knowledge that another man could be the child's father. Moral damage characterized. Situation that caused emotional upset and mental damage. Configuration of all the elements of civil liability. Sentence upheld. Appeal dismissed. (São Paulo. São Paulo Court of Justice. Civil Appeal No. 0028830-09.2010.826.0007 Rel. Ana Lúcia RomanholeMartucci. 6th Chamber of Private Law of the TJSP, Judged on 04/04/2014).

There is no need to talk about the non-repeatability of maintenance, when it comes to the granting of Pregnancy Maintenance and the bad faith adopted by the mother in favor of granting it.

CONCLUSION

The scope of this analysis was to discuss the legal protection of pregnancy maintenance for the unborn child, based on Law 11.804/08, studying the criteria for recognizing evidence of paternity.

Law 11.804/08, known as the Pregnancy Maintenance Law, came into force on November 5, 2008, as a way of ensuring the protection of the unborn child through the figure of the pregnant woman, taking into account the vulnerability that comprises the entire gestational period.

With this analysis, it is clear that, as this is a recent rule, it has generated countless discussions about the criteria used by magistrates to establish the amount that will be paid as maintenance by the alleged parent to the pregnant woman, through pregnancy maintenance. Since the determination of such payments is based on mere indications that lead to paternity, such as: testimony, photos, social networks, joint accounts, among others, associated with the trinomial need x possibility x reasonableness and also the Principle of Irrepeatability of Maintenance.

Thus, the research problem arose: To what extent is it possible to grant pregnancy maintenance in the event of uncertainty about the paternity of the unborn child?

This hypothesis was answered in the affirmative to the proposed problem, based on research into doctrinal, legal and jurisprudential arguments which were developed during the course of this Course Conclusion Work.

It was analyzed that current legislation does ensure the unborn child, giving them the right to pregnancy maintenance from the moment of conception, and the doctrine clarifies that the establishment of such maintenance when based on strong evidence that leads to possible paternity is fully possible even in the case of the unborn child, taking into account the criteria used by magistrates in the courts to reach this result.

From this perspective, it is clear that the unborn child does indeed have rights and duties protected from conception to birth, among which we have the right to maintenance, which is fundamental for it to thrive within its uterine life, as provided for in Article 2 of the Brazilian Civil Code of 2002. Of course, it is not enough for the pregnant woman to claim that the accusation of alleged father found in the case file is true. There must be strong evidence that paternity is true, which will be demystified through reliable evidence, in order to guarantee the alleged father legal security, so that he is not ordered to pay maintenance that is not his responsibility.

Finally, we looked at the theories and criteria in this case, the application of Law 11.804/08, clarifying, therefore, that child support is extremely important for maintaining the life of the unborn child, since for this to happen, it is necessary for the pregnant woman to have a healthy pregnancy. In addition, the law itself does not abandon the Defendant, determining in Article 6 that maintenance will only be set if there is evidence of paternity, guaranteeing the alleged father a fair and coherent decision.

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